

AI-PRISM

D5.2– Human robot collaboration behavioural analysis and modelling / Vigo & Silverline workshops

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AOI	Areas of Interest
MW	Mental Workload - an interaction between task requirements and the individual's capabilities or resources allocated to accomplish the task
Trust	The confidence that users have in the robot's reliability, competence, and ability to perform tasks as expected.
Skill acquisition	The process by which humans learn to effectively interact with, control, and collaborate with robots.
Physiological data	The biological measurements collected from humans, such as heart rate, skin conductance, and muscle activity. This data is used to monitor the physical and emotional states of individuals as they interact with robots.
Fluency	The smoothness and efficiency of the interactions between humans and robots. It involves the seamless coordination of actions and communication, resulting in an intuitive and uninterrupted workflow

Executive summary

The experiments in this report explored skill development, human-robot interaction, and teamwork in industrial settings.

Experiment 1 showed improvements in task performance, with better accuracy and response time, though higher task demands increased mental workload and stress.

Experiment 2 focused on trust, workload, and fluency in different human-robot tasks, showing variations based on task type.

Experiment 3 examined team dynamics, revealing that trust increased as more robots were involved, while fluency and workload fluctuated, with gender differences impacting the results.

Workshops further highlighted the potential of advanced technologies like collaborative robots and emphasized the importance of considering ergonomics and operator feedback.

The AI-PRISM project

AI-PRISM will provide industrial users with human-centred artificial intelligence (AI)-based solutions to create a more efficient, resilient, digital, sustainable, and high-quality European manufacturing industry.

To do so, we will develop an **integrated and scalable environment** with solutions adapted to dynamic and unpredictable manufacturing scenarios that require tasks that are difficult to automate and where speed and versatility are essential to meet users' needs. Furthermore, the solutions will be specific to semi-automated and collaborative manufacturing in flexible production processes and will not require specific robotic programming skills.

Our solutions ecosystem will have four main pillars.

1. **A human-centred collaborative robotic platform** oriented to ease hard-to-automate manufacturing tasks.
2. A human-robot cooperative environment powered by trustworthy AI.
3. **Social human-agent-robots teams' collaboration** — AI-based safety monitoring and robot control mechanisms to detect and avoid unsafe situations and ensure social and physical safety.
4. **An open-access network portal** to offer compliant infrastructure.

To evaluate our solutions' performance, transferability, scalability, and large-scale deployment, we will perform demonstrations in real operating environments. Specifically, in **four user pilots involving key manufacturing sectors** — furniture, food/beverage, built-in appliances, and electronics —, **types of robots and industrial processes that are difficult to automate, plus a generic demonstration facility**.

In addition to seeking quantitative improvements in the manufacturing sector, AI-PRISM aims to use technological innovation to support a paradigm shift in which AI, robotics and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) are integrated into the manufacturing domain for the improvement of flexible production processes, becoming a viable and widespread alternative for European factories.

During the next three years, **25 partners** from **12 countries** will join forces to make AI-PRISM a reality. From educational institutions to research and technology organisations, robot manufacturers, industries and use case providers; our interdisciplinary consortium brings together all the actors of the human-robot collaboration value chain and involves key experts in SSH, standardisation, exploitation, and dissemination.

Contents

Acronyms and definitions	5
Executive summary	6
List of Figures	10
List of Tables	10
1. Introduction.....	11
1.1. Aims and objectives	12
1.2. Research approach	12
2. Methodology	13
2.1. Experiment 1: Skill development and behavioural/physiological indicators of skill acquisition	13
2.1.1. Research Ethics	13
2.1.2. Procedure	13
2.1.3. Materials.....	14
2.2. Experiment 2: Investigating the Impact of Role Dynamics on Trust, Mental Workload, and Fluency in Human-Robot Interaction.....	15
2.2.1. Research Ethics	15
2.2.2. Procedure	15
2.2.3. Materials.....	16
2.3. Experiment 2: Investigating the Impact of Role Dynamics on Trust, Mental Workload, and Fluency in Human-Robot Interaction.....	16
2.3.1. Research Ethics	16
2.3.2. Procedure	17
2.3.3. Materials.....	17
2.4. Workshops.....	18
2.4.1. Research Ethics	18
2.4.2. Procedure	18
2.4.3. Materials.....	18
3. Results.....	19
3.1. Experiment 1: Skill development and behavioural/physiological indicators of skill acquisition	19

3.2. Experiment 2: Investigating the Impact of Role Dynamics on Trust, Mental Workload, and Fluency in Human-Robot Interaction.....	21
3.3. Experiment 3: Comparative laboratory study on Team Configurations: Single Robot vs. Multiple Robots.....	25
3.4. Workshops.....	29
3.4.1. Silverline	29
3.4.2. Vigo	30
4. Conclusions and future work.....	32
5. ANNEX A: References.....	34

List of Figures

Figure 1. Trust Levels Across Different Work Conditions and Task Types	22
Figure 2. Fluency Levels Across Different Work Conditions and Task Types.....	23
Figure 3. Mental Workload Levels Across Different Work Conditions and Task Types.....	24
Figure 4. Trust Levels Across Single and Multiple Robot Work Conditions and Task Types.....	26
Figure 5. Fluency Levels Across Single and Multiple Robot Work Conditions and Task Types.....	27
Figure 6. Mental Workload Levels Across Single and Multiple Robot Work Conditions and Task Types	28
Figure 7. Focus Group Workshop: Participant-Driven Process Re-design Using Sticker Drawings in Silverline	30
Figure 8. Focus Group Workshop: Participant-Driven Process Re-design Using Sticker Drawings in Vigo	31

List of Tables

Table 1. NASA TLX Factors means, Standard errors, and p-value comparing Performance Factor with Other Factors.....	19
Table 2. Eye Tracking Metrics as a FUNCTION of AOI and Error Count Performed in the Quality Inspection	21
Table 3. Eye Tracking fixation duration and number of visits in shared workspace, oversight and collaboration teams set up.....	25
Table 4. Eye Tracking fixation duration and number of visits in single robots versus multiple robots	29

1. Introduction

The rapid advancement of robotic systems and artificial intelligence (AI) has transformed numerous industries, necessitating a deeper understanding of human-robot interaction. This report adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative experiments and qualitative workshops, to investigate various facets of this interaction. The primary aim is to enhance the efficiency, safety, and satisfaction of operators working with robotic systems.

Three key experiments were conducted to address specific aspects of human-robot interaction within different industrial contexts:

1. **Experiment 1: Skill Development and Behavioural/Physiological Indicators of Skill Acquisition**
2. **Experiment 2: Investigating the Impact of Role Dynamics on Trust, Mental Workload, and Fluency in Human-Robot Interaction**
3. **Experiment 3: Comparative Laboratory Study on Team Configurations: Single Robot vs. Multiple Robots**

The experiments results can be beneficial for each of use case as discussed below:

- **ANDREU WORLD's furniture manufacturing processes**, including painting and sanding, which require skilled manual labour and are challenging to automate. Studying interactions with robots can reveal strategies to assist or augment these manual processes.
- **VIGO's** assembly of semiconductors, where operators manually position small electronic components with high precision. Understanding how operators acquire and refine these skills is crucial for developing training programs and automated systems that can support or enhance manual precision tasks.
- **ATHENIAN BREWERY's beverages production**, involving manual tasks such as transporting brewing powder, labelling kegs, assembling pallets, and sorting recycled glass bottles. Investigating collaborative systems in these contexts can lead to improved workflow efficiency and reduced operator fatigue.
- **SILVERLINE's hood assembly process**, particularly steps like grounding tests, visual inspections, and labelling. Evaluating the impact of multiple robots in these steps can highlight potential improvements in assembly line efficiency and product quality.
- **KEBA's testing of printed circuit boards (PCBs)**, where operators handle a fast-paced process of testing and sorting boards. This experiment can identify optimal collaboration models that enhance speed and accuracy while maintaining high safety standards.

Furthermore, qualitative data so far were collected through workshops conducted with Vigo and Silverline, featuring focus groups. Semi-structured interviews were conducted to gather in-depth insights into operators' perspectives on their current working setups. The interview

questions, formulated based on gaps identified in the task analysis, aimed to uncover operators' desired changes and suggestions for process improvements using AI-PRISM solutions. These interviews provided a comprehensive understanding of operators' experiences and preferences, offering valuable insights for designing more effective human-robot interaction systems.

1.1. Aims and objectives

The aim of the current work was to investigate the dynamics of human-robot interaction in various contexts, with a particular focus on skill acquisition, collaboration, and the impacts of different operational setups. In addition, it aimed to get the operators' perspectives on their current working setup and identify potential improvements using AI-PRISM imagery before implementing an actual solution.

The set of objectives needed to meet this aim are:

1. Understand how individuals acquire new skills with robotic systems and identify factors influencing the efficiency of skill acquisition (Experiment 1).
2. Evaluate the effectiveness of various human-robot collaboration systems and assess the impact of different monitoring conditions on human performance and satisfaction (Experiment 2).
3. Investigate the effects of single versus multiple robots on human operators and analyse how multiple robots influence communication and task performance (Experiment 3).
4. To identify operators' desired changes in their current working setup using AI-PRISM imagery before implementing solutions (Silverline and Vigo workshops).

1.2. Research approach

Social science research has established the importance of user centred research for the user increased acceptance (Pais et al., 2021). Research methodologies are critical in shaping the outcomes and validity of this field. Among these methodologies, quantitative and qualitative approaches stand out as foundational paradigms that guide researchers in collecting and analysing data (Clark et al., 2008). Each approach has distinct characteristics, advantages, and limitations, making them suitable for different types of research questions and contexts.

In this report, a mixed-methods approach was adopted, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative techniques. For Experiments 1, 2, and 3, a series of quantitative experiments were designed and conducted. Additionally, during the workshops, semi-structured interviews were carried out within focus groups to gather qualitative data. The interview questions were formulated based on gaps identified in the task analysis, aiming to understand operators' perspectives on their current working setup. Specifically, the questions sought to uncover what

changes the operators would like to make and what improvements they would suggest if they could alter the process using AI-PRISM imagery before implementing an actual solution. This qualitative data collection aimed to provide in-depth insights into the operators' experiences and preferences. The methodology reported in this deliverable will be presented in Section 2, with the results discussion in Section 3 and Section 4 outlining the conclusions and future directions.

2. Methodology

2.1. Experiment 1: Skill development and behavioural/physiological indicators of skill acquisition

The study involved twelve participants: all participants completed an inspection task on a computer monitor. Participants were aware that they were being observed, hence an overt observation took place. Three females (Mean Age = 30.5) and nine males (Mean Age = 27.3) completed this study.

2.1.1. Research Ethics

This research was approved by the Cranfield University Research Ethics Committee, and conducted in accordance with the Cranfield Research Integrity Policy, the British Psychological Society's Code of Human Research Ethics, and the General Data Protection Regulation 2018.

2.1.2. Procedure

Upon being briefed on the data collection aims, participants were guided through the informed consent and signed that they voluntarily agree to take part in the study. The NMPQ, IPS, CAAFI, TIPI, TSE and TR were completed prior to the inspection task. Participants were then assisted in putting on the eye tracking glasses, Empatica E4 wristband. The participants were then shown once how to complete the task with reference to an instructions sheet placed above the simulated testing area. The instructions were as follows:

1. Collects monitor A from **conveyor belt area** across to **testing area**.
2. Connect the **HDMI cable** to the monitors HDMI port.
3. Connect the **power cable** into the socket on the monitor, then connect the plug into the spare socket on the wall.
4. Switch the socket **on** at the wall.
5. Press the power button on the monitor to switch it on.
6. Once the monitor is on, using the mouse provided, head to Settings -> Display Settings -> **Advance Display Settings -> Properties -> Events**
7. Check the **DISPLAY** serial number against the check sheet.

8. Once serial number has been identified, press the **power button to switch the monitor off**.
9. Switch the **socket off** at the wall.
10. **Unplug** from the wall.
11. Disconnect the **power cable and HDMI cable**.
12. Perform quality Control: touch around the edges of the monitor to see if there are any identifiable scratches. If you detect any, please note it down in the list.
13. Place the monitor at **the end of the conveyor belt line** and begin the same process again with the next monitor(s).

The condition consisted of having a simulated conveyor belt area and a testing area for participants to navigate through the experiment. Participants lifted and collected one monitor at a time from the conveyor belt to the testing area, they were then required to plug the monitor into the laptop so that it was functioning correctly as well as then connecting the HDMI cable to the laptop where they could then check the serial number and code of the specific monitor provided. Participants had to navigate through the serial number check by using the mouse provided and noting down the serial number on a predefined checklist. They then completed an inspection check around the monitor by looking out for any scratches using their hands by feeling for any tactile information and noting this onto the predefined checklist before disconnecting all cables. After each inspection check, they were required to indicate their physical discomfort and stress level using scales provided. They then lifted the monitor and placed it back onto the conveyor belt. This process was then repeated for a total of 10 minutes, participants were then given instructions to complete the NASA TLX before returning to their session to complete an additional 10 minutes and this process was repeated overall 3 times.

2.1.3. Materials

2.1.3.1 Surveys

NASA TLX: The Mental Workload was measured using the NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX; Hart & Staveland, 1988). It measures participants' experience of a task across six different dimensions such as physical, temporal and mental demand, effort, frustration and performance. For each, the participant rates their experience across a 21-point scale.

Stress and Physical Discomfort Scale: Derived from the general labelled magnitude scale. The labelled magnitude scale (LMS) is a hybrid scaling technique using a verbally labelled line with quasi-logarithmic spacing between each label. The scale consists of a vertical line, which is marked with verbal anchors describing different intensities (e.g., "weak," "strong") (Jones et al., 2017).

2.1.3.2 Physiological Devices

Eye tracking glasses: Tobii Eye Tracking Glasses 3. The eye-tracking data was analysed using Tobii 3 eye-tracking analysis software, utilising the semantic gaze mapping focusing on the two

Areas of Interest (AOI) and investigating the average duration of fixations in these areas as well as number of visits.

Empatica E4: A wristwatch type device (Empatica E4) measured heart rate and electrodermal skin activity (EDA). Heart rate is known to increase with decreased physical comfort/increased activity and decrease with increased engagement/ trust (Edwards & Kelly, 2017), while EDA increase with increased discomfort and mental workload (Kosch et al., 2019).

2.2. Experiment 2: Investigating the Impact of Role Dynamics on Trust, Mental Workload, and Fluency in Human-Robot Interaction

The study involved twelve participants: all participants completed the oversight, collaboration and shared workspace team set-up scenarios. Participants were aware that they were being observed, hence an overt observation took place. 6 females (Mean Age = 29.5) and 6 males (Mean Age = 29.6). Participants had a variety of manufacturing experience from Not at all (2 people), little (6 people), moderate (3 people), a lot (1 people).

2.2.1. Research Ethics

This research was approved by the Cranfield University Research Ethics Committee, and conducted in accordance with the Cranfield Research Integrity Policy, the British Psychological Society's Code of Human Research Ethics, and the General Data Protection Regulation 2018.

2.2.2. Procedure

Upon being briefed on the data collection aims, participants were guided through the informed consent and signed that they voluntarily agree to take part in the study. The prequestionnaires including CAAFI, NASA TLX, TSE and TR was completed prior to the task. Participants were then assisted in putting on the eye tracking glasses. The participants were then shown once how to complete the task. Three different work scenarios involving robot interaction were presented to participants: shared workspace, oversight, and collaboration. In the shared workspace scenario, participants were required to perform a task within the same space as the robots without interacting with them. In the oversight scenario, participants observed the robots' performance without sharing the same space or interacting with them. In the collaboration scenario, participants actively interacted and collaborated with the robots to complete a task. Each scenario included three different conditions: control condition, physical demand condition, and mental demand condition. In the control condition, participants were asked to simply observe. In the physical demand condition, a heat patch was applied to the participants' backs to create a slight feeling of discomfort. The heat patch causes discomfort due to the sensation of intense heat (Olugbade et al., 2023; Williams et al., 2019). In the mental demand condition, participants were asked to count backwards from 100 in twos. All the conditions

were presented to participants in a counterbalanced order, and they filled out the Trust, fluency and Nasa TLX scales after each condition.

2.2.3. Materials

2.2.3.1 Surveys

NASA TLX: The Mental Workload was measured using the NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX; Hart & Staveland, 1988). It measures participants' experience of a task across six different dimensions such as physical, temporal and mental demand, effort, frustration and performance. For each, the participant rates their experience across a 21-point scale.

Furthermore, additional self-report measures were collected. These were included as Computer Aversion, Attitudes, and Familiarity Index (CAAFI), Technology self-efficacy (TSE), Technology readiness (TR) as well as Trust (2016) and Fluency (2022).

2.2.3.2 Physiological Devices

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2.3. Experiment 2: Investigating the Impact of Role Dynamics on Trust, Mental Workload, and Fluency in Human-Robot Interaction

The study involved twelve participants: all participants completed the single robot and multi-robot scenarios. Participants were aware that they were being observed, hence an overt observation took place. 6 females (Mean Age = 29.5) and 6 males (Mean Age = 29.6). Participants had a variety of manufacturing experience from Not at all (2 people), little (6 people), moderate (3 people), a lot (1 people).

2.3.1. Research Ethics

This research was approved by the Cranfield University Research Ethics Committee, and conducted in accordance with the Cranfield Research Integrity Policy, the British Psychological Society's Code of Human Research Ethics, and the General Data Protection Regulation 2018.

2.3.2. Procedure

Upon being briefed on the data collection aims, participants were guided through the informed consent and signed that they voluntarily agree to take part in the study. The prequestionnaires including CAAFI, NASA TLX, TSE and TR was completed prior to the task. Participants were then assisted in putting on the eye tracking glasses. The participants were then shown once how to complete the task. Two different work scenarios involving robot interaction were presented to participants: single robot vs multi robot. Each scenario included three different conditions: control condition, physical demand condition, and mental demand condition. In the control condition, participants were asked to simply observe. In the physical demand condition, a heat patch was applied to the participants' backs to create a slight feeling of discomfort. In the mental demand condition, participants were asked to count backwards from 100 in twos. All the conditions were presented to participants in a counterbalanced order, and they filled out the Trust, fluency and Nasa TLX after each condition.

2.3.3. Materials

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NASA TLX: The Mental Workload was measured using the NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX; Hart & Staveland, 1988). It measures participants' experience of a task across six different dimensions such as physical, temporal and mental demand, effort, frustration and performance. For each, the participant rates their experience across a 21-point scale.

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Empatica E4: A wristwatch type device (Empatica E4) measured heart rate and electrodermal skin activity (EDA). Heart rate is known to increase with decreased physical comfort/increased activity and decrease with increased engagement/ trust (Edwards & Kelly, 2017), while EDA increase with increased discomfort and mental workload (Kosch et al., 2019).

2.4. Workshops

Operators were recruited for Silverline and Vigo engagement workshops. In Silverline, 5 operators were recruited with a work experience of three years or more (3 males and 1 female). In Vigo, 5 operators were recruited from up to 1 year experience to 20 years' work experience (4 males, 1 female).

2.4.1. Research Ethics

This research was approved by the Cranfield University Research Ethics Committee, and conducted in accordance with the Cranfield Research Integrity Policy, the British Psychological Society's Code of Human Research Ethics, and the General Data Protection Regulation 2018.

2.4.2. Procedure

A diverse group of operators relevant to the study topic was selected. Next, a structured discussion guide with key questions and topics was developed. The session was then conducted in a neutral environment, with a facilitator ensuring all participants had the opportunity to contribute. Finally, the session was recorded, transcribed, and the data was analysed to identify common themes and insights.

2.4.3. Materials

2.4.3.1 Focus group questions

Participants were presented with a series of questions about the current process and available technologies that could be incorporated into manufacturing, such as collaborative robotics, augmented/virtual reality, and smart assistive technology. The discussion also covered processes where operators could see the potential of these technologies and how they could be implemented.

2.4.3.2 Imagery visuals

Participants watched a video of the existing process, which emphasized the human factors and ergonomics impact, providing a visual understanding of the current challenges. Using visual materials such as stickers and markers, they were given a basic layout of the workstation and asked to re-design it. Participants placed stickers or drew on the layout to indicate the operator's position, identified the technology support needed, and suggested further improvements to enhance the process.

3. Results

3.1. Experiment 1: Skill development and behavioural/physiological indicators of skill acquisition

Response Time and Accuracy: It was shown that there was an increase in the development of skill acquisition whereby participants displayed a decrease in error count (from 1 to 0 over the inspection of 30 minutes), instruction analysis and increase in time of task completions as the average time reduced from 3 minutes 20 seconds (SD = 0.08) for the first component to 1 minute 48 seconds (SD = 0.03) for the last component. The Spearman's rho correlation indicated a strong negative effect ($\rho = -0.794$, $p = .00$, $n = 10$). Taking together accuracy and response time, results indicate that as time goes by participants acquire the new skill and internalise the task instructions/acquire the manual skill needed for the task.

Mental Workload: One of the main interests of the study were the changes in the mental workload through skill acquisition. The NASA TLX scores were repeated in the intervals of 10 minutes capturing the initial response, mid-process and late response to the task on six factors of Mental Demand, Temporal Demand, Physical Demand, Effort, Performance, and Frustration. A 6 by 3 repeated measures ANOVA (6 factors of NASA TLX vs 3-time windows) showed the main effect of Factor to be significant ($F(5, 50) = 13.07$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = .566$). The main effect of time and the interaction Factor by Time were not significant ($p > .189$). Post hoc analysis of the main effect of Factor with Bonferroni correction indicated that Performance factors was higher evaluated than other factors ($p < .023$, Table 1), however there were no other significant differences.

<i>Factor</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Performance vs other factors p value</i>
Mental Demand	3.152	0.574	0.002
Physical Demand	4.636	0.646	0.024
Temporal Demand	4	0.615	0.003
Performance	8.545	0.369	
Effort	3.939	0.572	0.003
Frustration	3.636	0.7	0.023

Table 1. NASA TLX Factors means, Standard errors, and p-value comparing Performance Factor with Other Factors.

Physiological Data: The second step of the analysis was concerning physiological markers of the skill acquisition. As the behavioural data indicated decreasing response time for completing the task (participants were quicker over time) the data was segmented into three sections: early task performance 0:00-10:00 minutes, mid performance 10:01-20:00 minutes and late performance 20:01 – 30:00 minutes. These three-time windows were used to compare the data

with non-parametric Friedman repeated measures test to see whether there were differences in physiological data (EDA, HR, Skin Temperature) depending on the task duration. The only approaching significance result was observed with the heart rate ($\chi^2 = 5.17$, $p = .08$). Further investigation with Wilcoxon Signed Rank test showed that participants heart rate was significantly lower during the first 10-minute window compared to the second 10-minute window ($Z = 2.20$, $p = .028$) and at a trend level lower than in the third time window ($Z = 1.65$, $p = .099$), however there was no significance between first- and third-time windows ($p = .470$).

To test whether and how the physiological data and self-report task load scores relate to each other, non-parametric Spearman's rho correlation was performed. The results from the physiological data show that the initial 10 minutes of the task showed a positive significant correlation between EDA and NASA TLX Effort score (Spearman rho = .675, $p = .016$), the second set of 10 minutes positively correlated EDA and NASA TLX Temporal Demands (Spearman rho = .757, $p = .004$), while final 10 minutes showed a positive correlation between EDA and NASA TLX Physical demand (Spearman rho = .639, $p = .025$) and Mental demand (Spearman's rho = .580, $p = 0.048$). Interestingly, neither heart rate, nor skin temperature ratings correlated with NASA TLX scores.

Eye Tracking: Finally, to understand how participants are learning the new task, eye tracking gaze mapping and fixation duration analysis was performed with Tobii eye tracking glasses 3. Two areas of interest (AOI) were defined – the written instructions displayed in front of assembly area, and the monitors themselves. The preliminary results suggest that unsurprisingly participants had larger durations of fixations and number of visits to the monitor AOI compared to instruction AOI (Table 2). Interestingly, number of visits to instruction AOI was related to number of errors participants performed in the assembly. Further analysis will consider the changes in fixation duration during three-time windows as well as changes in fixation count and its relationship to the errors in the assembly.

Participant	Total duration of fixations		Number of Visits		
	Monitor	Instructions	Monitor	Instructions	Errors
1	236949	8595	989	45	2
2	258417	3216	1053	1	3
3	28882	1072	17	2	1
4	6792	0	9	0	1
5	26569	0	35	0	0
6	1803	0	9	0	2
8	60730	0	110	0	1
9	9397	0	20	0	1
10	7323	0	20	0	0
11	87768	11691	201	63	0

12	1513	0	7	0	0
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Table 2. Eye Tracking Metrics as a FUNCTION of AOI and Error Count Performed in the Quality Inspection

3.2. Experiment 2: Investigating the Impact of Role Dynamics on Trust, Mental Workload, and Fluency in Human-Robot Interaction

The study employed a 3x3 within-subject design to explore variations in participants' trust, fluency, and mental workload scores across shared workspace, collaboration and oversight conditions, taking into account different task demands (control, physical demand, mental demand) in interactions with robots.

Trust: Regarding Trust in robots—the willingness and confidence individuals have in relying on robots for tasks, decisions, or interactions— descriptive results showed that in different work conditions, trust levels vary depending on the type of tasks involved. In shared work conditions, there's high trust in control tasks, moderate trust in physical demands, and low trust in mental demands. In oversight conditions, trust is moderate in control tasks, higher in physical demands, and lower in mental demand. Collaboration conditions prioritize moderate trust in mental demand, high trust in physical demands, and low trust in control tasks (Figure 1). The inferential results however indicated no significant main effects for work conditions ($F(2, 20) = 0.16, p > .05, \eta^2 = .016$) or task demands ($F(2, 20) = 3.08, p > .05, \eta^2 = .236$). In addition, no significant difference was found between males and females ($F(1, 10) = 0.659, p > .05, \eta^2 = .062$).

Figure 1. Trust Levels Across Different Work Conditions and Task Types

Fluency: In examining fluency across different work conditions, the descriptive results revealed distinct patterns for control, physical demand, and mental demand tasks. The level of fluency was highest in shared workspace conditions, followed by a decrease in oversight condition, and was lowest in collaboration condition across all tasks demands (Figure 2). Similar to the trust variable, the inferential results however indicated no significant main effects for work conditions ($F(2, 20) = 1.75, p > .05, \eta^2 = .149$) nor task demands ($F(2, 20) = 2.51, p > .05, \eta^2 = .154$) in fluency. In addition, no significant difference was found between males and females ($F(1, 10) = 0.188, p > .05, \eta^2 = .018$).

Figure 2. Fluency Levels Across Different Work Conditions and Task Types

Mental Workload: In examining mental workload across different work conditions, the descriptive results showed that in the control condition, mental workload decreased dramatically from the shared workspace scenario to the oversight scenario, reaching its lowest point in the collaboration scenario. Conversely, in the mental demand and physical demand conditions, mental workload gradually increased from the shared workspace scenario to the oversight scenario, and then further in the collaboration scenario (Figure 3). Therefore, for tasks with higher mental or physical demands, collaboration with robots increases mental workload compared to shared workspace and oversight conditions. Furthermore, the inferential analysis showed a significant main effect of task demand ($F(2, 20) = 4.58, p < .05, \eta^2 = .315$), however no significant main effects for work conditions ($F(2, 20) = .475, p > .05, \eta^2 = .045$) nor interaction were found ($F(2, 20) = 2.41, p > .05, \eta^2 = .195$). In addition, no significant differences were found between men and women ($F(1, 10) = .88, p > .05, \eta^2 = .081$). Moreover, the post hoc comparisons with Bonferroni correction revealed a difference in mental workload between control condition and mental demand condition ($p > .05$). Therefore, task demand significantly affects mental workload, while work conditions and gender do not. Additionally, there was a notable difference in mental workload between control and mental demand conditions.

Figure 3. Mental Workload Levels Across Different Work Conditions and Task Types

Furthermore, an independent sample test was conducted to determine if there are any differences between men and women on Computer Aversion, Attitudes, and Familiarity Index (CAAFI), Technology self-efficacy (TSE) and Technology readiness (TR). The results showed no significant difference between these groups.

Physiological Data: To understand how the physiological data and self-report scores (Trust, fluency, NASA TLX) in shared workspace, oversight and collaboration a non-parametric Spearman's rho correlation was conducted. The results showed no significant correlation between EDA and HR with self-report scores. Furthermore, in terms of gender differences no significant differences were observed for EDA and HR scores between men and women in all conditions.

Eye Tracking: To understand how participants work in different team setups, eye tracking gaze mapping and fixation duration analysis were performed using Tobii Eye Tracking Glasses 3. Three areas of interest (AOI) were defined: the shared workspace, oversight, and collaboration. Preliminary results indicate that participants unsurprisingly had longer fixation durations and more visits to the collaboration and oversight AOIs compared to the shared workspace AOI (Table 3).

Participant	Total duration of fixations			Number of Visits		
	Collaboration	Oversight	Shared workspace	Collaboration	Oversight	Shared workspace
1	524621	32541	0	954	656	222
2	658892	56421	235	1235	166	0
3	321256	2112	0	111	22	0
4	56213	1235	0	262	4123	0
5	456212	55645	1053	350	161	0
6	22563	78951	0	352	4585	645
8	11235	5865	0	414	946	261
9	10234	4561	0	516	745	0
10	4562	7895	1321	476	562	0
11	98564	453325	11691	652	965	466
12	35261	789623	0	586	987	0

Table 3. Eye Tracking fixation duration and number of visits in shared workspace, oversight and collaboration teams set up

3.3. Experiment 3: Comparative laboratory study on Team Configurations: Single Robot vs. Multiple Robots

The study utilized a 3x2 within-subject design to investigate variations in participants' trust, fluency, and mental workload across different task demands (control, physical demand, mental demand) during interactions with single robots versus multiple robots.

Trust: The descriptive results showed an increase in trust scores from single robots to multiple robots across all tasks demands (control, physical demand, mental demand). However, in the physical demand condition, participants exhibited more trust in robots compared to the control and mental demand conditions (figure 4). However, the inferential results showed no main effects for single robot versus multiple robot work conditions ($F(1, 10) = 0.761, p > .05, \eta^2 = .071$) or task demands ($F(2, 20) = .447, p > .05, \eta^2 = .043$). In addition, no significant difference was found between males and females ($F(1, 10) = 1.29, p > .05, \eta^2 = .115$)

Figure 4. Trust Levels Across Single and Multiple Robot Work Conditions and Task Types

Fluency: In terms of Fluency, the descriptive results indicated that in the control condition, fluency increased when participants worked with multiple robots compared to single robots. However, in the physical demand and mental demand conditions, fluency decreased from single robots to multiple robots (Figure 5). Inferential analysis however, showed no significant main effect of single robots versus multiple robots ($F(1, 10) = 0.258, p > .05, \eta^2 = .025$). Similarly, no significant main effect of task demands was observed for this condition ($F(2, 20) = 0.116, p > .05, \eta^2 = .194$). In addition, there was no significant differences between men and women ($F(1, 10) = 0.172, p > .05, \eta^2 = .017$). However, the result showed a significant interaction between task demand and gender ($F(2, 20) = 5.14, p < .05, \eta^2 = .340$) which revealed that the influence of task demands on the fluency variable is different for men and women.

Figure 5. Fluency Levels Across Single and Multiple Robot Work Conditions and Task Types

Mental workload: When examining mental workload across single versus multiple work conditions, considering different task demands (control, physical demand, and mental demand), the descriptive results revealed an increase in mental workload scores from single robots to multiple robots in the control condition. However, the opposite pattern was observed for the mental demand task, where mental workload decreased from single robots to multiple robots. For the physical demand condition, mental workload remained consistent for both single and multiple robots (Figure 6). The inferential results also showed a significant main effect of task demand ($F(2, 20) = 4.35, p < .05, \eta^2 = .303$), but no significant main effect of work conditions (single vs multiple) ($F(1, 10) = 2.32, p > .05, \eta^2 = .189$) or gender ($F(1, 10) = 0.819, p > .05, \eta^2 = .076$) were found. In addition, a significant interaction was found for work condition and task demands ($F(2, 20) = 3.77, p < .05, \eta^2 = .274$) and for work condition and gender ($F(1, 10) = 10.67, p < .05, \eta^2 = .516$).

The post hoc analysis using Bonferroni correction showed that a difference in mental workload scores ($P < .05$) in control condition and mental demand task condition. The significant differences between control and mental demand tasks indicate that mental tasks are particularly impactful on mental workload, more so than control tasks.

Figure 6. Mental Workload Levels Across Single and Multiple Robot Work Conditions and Task Types

Furthermore, an independent sample test was conducted to determine if there are any differences between men and women on Computer Aversion, Attitudes, and Familiarity Index (CAAFI), Technology self-efficacy (TSE) and Technology readiness (TR). The results showed no significant difference between these groups.

Physiological Data: To understand how the physiological data and self-report scores in multi robot and single robot conditions relate to each other, a non-parametric Spearman's rho correlation was performed. The results from the physiological data showed no correlation between EDA and HR with NASA TLX, fluency and trust in both conditions. In terms of gender differences, the descriptive results showed that men generally had higher scores for EDA in all conditions compared to women. Conversely, women reported higher scores for HR in all conditions compared to men. The inferential analysis (independent-sample T-test) showed significant differences between men ($M=76.42$, $SD=1.50$) and women ($M=82.79$, $SD=13.6$) for HR in the mental demand condition when working with multiple robots $t(-.779) = 7$, $P=0.01$.

Eye Tracking: To understand how participants work in different team setups for single robots versus multiple robots, eye tracking gaze mapping and fixation duration analysis were performed using Tobii Eye Tracking Glasses 3. Two areas of interest (AOI) were defined: working with single robots vs multiple robots. The results showed that participants had longer fixation durations and more visits to the multiple robots compared to the single robot AOI (Table 4).

Participant	Total duration of fixations		Number of Visits	
	Single Robot	Multi Robots	Single Robot	Multi Robots
1	524621		954	
2	658892	886545	1235	1103
3	321256	665856	111	1500
4	56213	771895	262	563
5	456212	85610	350	445
6	22563	616641	352	2102
8	11235	485454	414	996
9	10234	88542	516	946
10	4562	11411	476	745
11	98564	5642	652	889
12	35261	124568	586	2011
		9623		987

Table 4. Eye Tracking fixation duration and number of visits in single robots versus multiple robots

3.4. Workshops

Two workshops have been conducted so far, utilizing focus groups composed of participants from Vigo and Silverline companies. These focus groups provided valuable information and feedback during the workshops. The results of these sessions can be found below:

3.4.1. Silverline

Main Challenges: The main challenges identified by operators at Silverline during the process included several key issues. Firstly, operators reported difficulty in noticing certain faults when relying solely on visual and tactile information, which can compromise the accuracy and reliability of the inspection process. Additionally, the physical difficulty of handling components was noted, particularly when dealing with larger or more cumbersome parts, which can lead to increased physical strain and potential ergonomic issues. The requirement to apply multiple barcodes to components was also highlighted as a challenge, as it adds complexity and time to the process. Furthermore, operators experienced mental fatigue due to the repetitive nature of the tasks, which can impact concentration and overall efficiency. These challenges underscore the need for improvements in process design and operator support to enhance productivity and reduce the strain on workers.

Figure 7. Focus Group Workshop: Participant-Driven Process Re-design Using Sticker Drawings in Silverline

Future Process and Feedback to Tech Providers: Several improvements were suggested to address these challenges. Operators recommended the use of AI vision control systems to alert when materials or steps are forgotten, enhancing accuracy and reducing human error. It was proposed that robots perform ground and electrical tests, thereby eliminating the physical strain on operators by automating the task of moving faulty components aside. For labelling, a more efficient solution was needed, such as applying multiple stickers or using a single barcode that AI can verify, ensuring that missed labels are detected. Additionally, operators suggested that robots could handle packaging tasks. However, there are concerns that increased automation might reduce social interaction among operators, potentially leading to feelings of isolation and boredom. It is also crucial to consider the implications of automation errors and establish protocols for such scenarios. Moreover, incorporating natural voice interfaces for communication in the operator's native language, as well as touch screens and visual interfaces like indicator lights, would improve user interaction and control. Ultimately, while automation can significantly enhance efficiency, it is vital to ensure that operators retain control over the robots to maintain a balanced and effective workflow.

3.4.2. Vigo

Main Challenges: The main challenges identified included the high precision and time required for tasks such as calibration under the microscope, the gluing process (ensuring the application of the correct amount of glue) and waxing the plate to achieve an even height. Additionally, there was a risk of wires bending at the tip, which could compromise the quality and reliability

of the final product. These challenges highlight the need for meticulous attention to detail and careful handling during the manufacturing process to maintain high standards and prevent defects.

Figure 8. Focus Group Workshop: Participant-Driven Process Re-design Using Sticker Drawings in Vigo

Future Process and Feedback to Tech Providers: To address these challenges, participants proposed several improvements aimed at enhancing efficiency and precision. One suggestion was to deploy robotic systems for positioning and calibration tasks, while maintaining operator oversight to verify these actions. The overarching aim is to automate processes extensively to streamline operations. For the measurement process, participants recommended implementing data sharing across different machines to ensure consistent production and enable early error detection. They emphasized the importance of remote access and control to enhance operational flexibility, alongside advancements in measurement and calibration methodologies. While AI-driven calibration was considered feasible, participants stressed the ongoing need for human supervision to ensure accuracy and reliability.

Despite the potential reduction in certain operator tasks, the overall efficiency and time management of operations would be enhanced. Operators expressed the need for real-time monitoring through all cameras, continuous awareness of process status (e.g., start, cancel, errors), and visible status indicators for positioning tables. Additionally, participants highlighted the importance of implementing safety measures, such as protective covers, to mitigate risks in case of operational issues.

4. Conclusions and future work

The conducted experiments in this report provided valuable insights into skill development, human-robot interaction dynamics, and team configurations in industrial settings:

- In Experiment 1, participants demonstrated notable improvements in task accuracy and response time, indicating successful skill acquisition. Mental workload, as measured by NASA TLX, was significantly impacted by task performance, with physiological data suggesting correlations between stress indicators and task demands. Eye-tracking data revealed the importance of visual attention in reducing errors, highlighting the role of instructional guidance in skill development.
- Experiment 2 explored trust, mental workload, and fluency in various human-robot interaction scenarios. Although no significant main effects were found, descriptive results indicated that task demand and work conditions influenced these variables, with physical and mental tasks affecting trust and workload differently.
- Experiment 3 focused on team configurations, revealing that trust increased with multiple robots, while fluency and mental workload showed complex patterns depending on task demands. Notably, gender differences influenced fluency and workload, suggesting the need for tailored approaches in diverse workforces. The workshops further underscored the potential for integrating advanced technologies like collaborative robots and augmented reality in manufacturing processes, emphasizing the need for ergonomic considerations and operator feedback.

Future research should build on these findings by exploring longer-term skill acquisition and retention, as well as investigating the impacts of different instructional methods. One particularly interesting area for future study is the use of emerging technologies, such as instructional videos featuring avatars. Examining how voice interactions and scripted dialogues influence participant choices and smooth interactions could provide significant understanding. This could enhance the effectiveness of training programs and improve the overall user experience in human-robot collaborative environments. Furthermore, the next phase of this research can further develop the interface by incorporating advanced interaction functionality. This phase can assess user experience (UX) in terms of trust, fluency, and mental workload, with a focus on satisfaction and goal achievement.

Finally, the last phase of user engagement involves conducting remaining workshops in Andreu Worlds, Athenian Brewery and KEBA aimed at addressing current challenges in the process. Since the operators have varying levels of English proficiency, the workshops will focus on minimal verbal communication and instead emphasize hands-on activities and visual aids to foster innovative solutions. These workshops draw inspiration from prior work on visual signage (Eimontaite, 2022; Gwilt et al., 2018) and the use of LEGO to enhance stakeholder engagement (de Saille et al., 2022). This approach has previously proven effective in bridging

communication gaps between robotics engineers and shopfloor operators, leading to increased acceptance of new processes (Eimontaite et al., 2022) and improved trust in human-robot interactions (Cameron & Collins, 2021). As a result, the engagement program anticipates several outcomes: (i) heightened user engagement and acceptance of the new procedures; (ii) enhanced technology readiness and increased trust in automation; and (iii) improved transparency regarding process changes and assembly, thereby fostering stronger organizational commitment.

5. ANNEX A: References

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